

THE AERODYNAMIC INFLUENCE OF BLADE GEOMETRY ON THE FORMATION OF HELICOPTER ROTOR THRUST

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Abstract

This article examines the influence of rotor blade geometry on the distribution of aerodynamic forces and the magnitude of thrust generated. A comparative analysis of rectangular and sabre-shaped blades is conducted based on theoretical relationships linking lift, drag, and effective flow velocity. It is established that the sabre-shaped blade provides a more uniform lift distribution along the radius and reduces localized pressure peaks, thereby minimizing wave losses. Calculated data demonstrates that a slight reduction in integral thrust improves the overall rotor performance, reducing drag and vibration and increasing flow stability. The results confirm that sabre-shaped geometry is an effective means of optimizing rotor systems in modern helicopters, where stability, reliability, and reduced acoustic performance at high rotation speeds are priorities.

Keywords: aerodynamics, helicopter, blade geometry, rotor, saber-shaped form.

Introduction: The rotor is a key element of a helicopter's aerodynamic design, determining its primary flight and performance characteristics. The blade geometry and aerodynamic performance directly impact the aircraft's thrust, vibration loads, acoustic characteristics, and fuel efficiency. Over the past decades, rotor design has undergone significant improvements, ranging from simple rectangular blades to complex spatial profiles with optimized twist and tip shapes [2, pp. 24–28]. However, despite increased flight speeds (over 300 km/h) and reduced structural weight, modern helicopters remain sources of intense noise and vibration, significantly limiting their operational capabilities [3, pp. 119–123].

The primary source of noise is the flow generated by the rotating rotor blades. Their interaction with the vortex wakes generates high-amplitude shock waves, generating so-called blade slap—an impulsive noise characteristic of most rotorcraft [5, pp. 176–179]. This phenomenon is caused by the formation of shock waves at the blade tips when transonic Mach numbers are reached. To reduce shock losses, it is necessary to lower the effective Mach number, which is achieved by curving the shock front and creating an oblique shock relative to the airflow direction [6, pp. 245–247].

Previously, attempts were made to reduce the acoustic impact by reducing the rotor speed and narrowing its tips. However, these solutions were accompanied by a decrease in efficiency and a deterioration in lift properties, making them unacceptable for most flight tasks [8, pp. 201–205]. Increasing the number of blades, in turn, led to an increase in weight and higher

operating costs. Consequently, the most promising direction for modernization is the optimization of the blade shape, ensuring a favorable balance between aerodynamic efficiency, noise characteristics, and strength parameters [9, pp. 311–314].

Modern research shows that sabre-shaped (or deflected-tip) blades offer significant advantages over traditional rectangular and trapezoidal shapes. Their spatial geometry helps mitigate wave effects, reduce the amplitude of vortex structures, and, consequently, lower noise levels [1, pp. 119–122]. Furthermore, the smooth radial load distribution contributes to improved aerodynamic performance and flow stability behind the propeller disk [4, pp. 88–93].

Another important aspect is the influence of blade geometry on the distribution of lift coefficient along the radius. In the presence of twist, the angle of attack of the sections changes, which causes variations in local lift coefficients and affects the integral characteristics of the propeller [3, pp. 119–123]. To analyze these patterns, this paper considers rectangular and saber-shaped blades, modeled under identical boundary conditions. The study aims to identify patterns of thrust variation, pressure distribution, and aerodynamic losses depending on blade shape.

The aim of this study is to comparatively analyze the aerodynamic characteristics of rectangular and saber-shaped helicopter rotor blades, with an emphasis on the thrust distribution, C_t and C_p coefficients, and the integral FM efficiency depending on the profile geometric parameters.

Figure 1. Azimuthal positions of elements of rectangular and saber-shaped blades at the same radius.

Figure 1 shows the azimuthal positions of the elements of a rectangular and a saber-shaped blade, located on the same radius. This diagram allows one to clearly trace the change in the angle ψ_i along the radius, depending on the blade shape. For a rectangular blade, this angle is constant in all cross-sections, while for a saber-shaped blade, it changes due to the curvature of the tip and the non-uniform distribution of the chord curvature [6, pp. 245–247].

The airflow velocity experienced by each blade element consists of two components—the circumferential and the translational velocity. The resulting total velocity of the element at a radius r_i is expressed by formula (1):

$$W_{r_i} = \omega r_i + V_{xHB} \sin \psi_i \quad (1)$$

Here ω is the angular velocity of the main rotor, rad/s; r_i is the radius of the section under consideration, m; V_{xHB} is the horizontal component of the helicopter flight speed in the plane of rotor rotation, m/s; ψ_i is the azimuthal position of the blade element, deg.

This relationship shows that the local velocity W_{r_i} is determined not only by the radius and angular velocity, but also by the azimuthal position of the blade. The expression also includes the projection of the translational velocity onto the rotor shaft axis and the induced air velocity directed opposite to the oncoming flow [5, pp. 176–179]. $V_y = V \sin A$

From formula (1) it follows that for the same radius but different ψ_i , the values of W_{r_i} will differ, especially for a saber-shaped blade. This leads to a change in the distribution of lift and pressure along the radius. For a rectangular blade, ψ_i does not change, and, consequently, the velocity distribution remains axisymmetric. For a saber-shaped blade, on the contrary, a shift in the velocity front occurs, which causes a redistribution of the load and reduces the intensity of the vortex wakes [6, pp. 245–247; 7, pp. 189–195].

To determine the local aerodynamic characteristics of each blade section, the dependence of the lift and drag coefficients on the angle of attack of the profile is used, presented in the form: and , These dependencies allow us to calculate the components of the resulting aerodynamic force dR_{r_i} for a given blade element - the

lift force and the drag force, which are determined by the formulas [8, pp. 200–204].

$$c_y = f(\alpha) c_x = f_1(\alpha) d\bar{Y}_{r_i} d\bar{X}_{r_i}$$

The local lift force acting on a blade element at radius r_i is calculated using the expression

$$dY_{r_i} = (2) c_{y_{r_i}} \frac{\rho W_{r_i}^2}{2} b_{r_i} dr_i$$

Here, ρ is the air density, kg/m³; W_{r_i} is the local flow velocity around the blade element, m/s; b_{r_i} is the airfoil chord length at a given cross-section, m; dr_i is the radius length element, m. The coefficient $c_{y_{r_i}}$ reflects the airfoil's ability to generate lift at a given angle of attack and Mach number. The higher the $c_{y_{r_i}}$ value, the more efficiently the cross-section converts flow energy into lift.

Similarly, the drag force arising at the same radius is determined by the relation

$$dX_{r_i} = (3) c_{x_{r_i}} \frac{\rho W_{r_i}^2}{2} b_{r_i} dr_i$$

The coefficient $c_{x_{r_i}}$ characterizes the energy losses due to overcoming air resistance and reflects the quality of the aerodynamic profile shape. For saber-shaped blades, the $c_{x_{r_i}}$ value is generally lower due to a more rational pressure distribution along the chord, which reduces parasitic losses [7, pp. 189–195].

The resulting aerodynamic force dR_{r_i} is the vector sum of lift and drag. Since these forces act at an angle to each other, the resulting vector deviates from the direction of lift by an angle μ , which is determined by the expression

$$\mu = \arctg \frac{dX_{r_i}}{dY_{r_i}} = \arctg \frac{c_{x_{r_i}}}{c_{y_{r_i}}}$$

The coefficient $c_{x_{r_i}}$ characterizes the energy losses due to overcoming air resistance and reflects the quality of the aerodynamic profile shape. For saber-shaped blades, the $c_{x_{r_i}}$ value is generally lower due to a more rational pressure distribution along the chord, which reduces parasitic losses [7, pp. 189–195].

The resulting aerodynamic force dR_{r_i} is the vector sum of lift and drag. Since these forces act at an angle

to each other, the resulting vector deviates from the direction of lift by an angle μ , which is determined by the expression

$$\mu = \frac{1}{K}$$

Small values of μ correspond to high aerodynamic qualities of the profile, which means minimal energy losses due to drag and, as a result, increased efficiency of the main rotor.

To estimate the contribution of each component of the force in the axial and tangential directions, the lift force dY_{ri} and the drag force dX_{ri} are projected onto the axis of rotation and onto the plane of rotation of the propeller. This results in expressions for the elementary thrust force dP_{ri} and the drag force in the plane of rotation dX_{pvr_i} [9, pp. 311–314]:

$$dP_{ri} = (4)dY_{ri} \cos \beta_{ri} - dX_{ri} \sin \beta_{ri} = (c_{y_{ri}} \cos \beta_{ri} - c_{x_{ri}} \sin \beta_{ri}) \rho \frac{W_{ri}^2}{2} b_{ri} dr_i$$

Here, β_{ri} is the flow inlet angle, which determines the inclination of the resulting airflow relative to the plane of rotation. The first term of the expression describes the axial component of lift, and the second describes the tangential component of drag, which reduces effective thrust.

Similarly, the drag force in the plane of rotation is determined by the relationship

$$dX_{nbr_i} = dX_{ri} \cos \beta_{ri} + dY_{ri} \sin \beta_{ri} = (c_{y_{ri}} \sin \beta_{ri} + c_{x_{ri}} \cos \beta_{ri}) \rho \frac{W_{ri}^2}{2} b_{ri} dr_i \quad (5)$$

Due to the smallness of the angle of incidence, it can be assumed that β_{ri}

$$\sin \beta_{ri} \approx \beta_{ri},$$

And,

$$\cos \beta_{ri} \approx 1 - dX_{ri} \sin \beta_{ri} \approx 0$$

The first term in equation (7) corresponds to the effect of profile drag, while the second reflects the influence of lift, which creates a moment of resistance to rotation. For saber-shaped blades, the contribution of the second term is reduced because the change in angle β_{ri} along the radius occurs more smoothly. This leads to a reduction in energy losses and an increase in the FM efficiency coefficient [10, pp. 118–126].

Since the inflow angle β_{ri} is small in most operating modes of the rotor ($\beta_{ri} \leq 5^\circ$), it is permissible to use the approximations $\sin \beta_{ri} \approx \beta_{ri}$ and $\cos \beta_{ri} \approx 1$. This allows us to simplify expressions (6) – (7) to more convenient engineering forms. In this case, the influence of the term $dX_{ri} \sin \beta_{ri}$ can be neglected, since its contribution to the resulting thrust is insignificant [9, pp. 311–314].

Taking these assumptions into account, the expression for the elementary thrust force of the blade element takes the form:

$$dP_{ri} \approx dY_{ri} = c_{y_{ri}} \rho \frac{W_{ri}^2}{2} b_{ri} dr_i$$

This means that, to a first approximation, the elementary thrust coincides with the projection of the local lift force onto the axis of rotation. In other words, almost all of the generated lift force is used to create useful axial thrust, which is especially true for blades with a low pitch angle and optimized tip geometry [10, pp. 118–126].

For the elementary drag force in the plane of rotation, including the contribution of both the profile drag and the inclined component of the lift force, we obtain:

$$dX_{nbr_i} \approx dX_{ri} + dY_{ri} \beta_{ri} = dX_{ri} + dY_{ri} \frac{V_1}{\omega r_i}$$

Here, V_1 is the axial (induced) velocity of the flow through the propeller disk, and ωr_i is the peripheral velocity of the element. This expression shows that as the induced velocity increases, the contribution of the second term increases, leading to increased rotational energy losses. For saber-shaped blades, this effect is less pronounced due to the smoother change in angle β_{ri} along the radius and fewer pressure surges at the tips.

Substituting relations (2) and (3) into this expression, we obtain the final form for dX_{pvr_i} :

$$dX_{nbr_i} = (c_{y_{ri}} \beta_{ri} + c_{x_{ri}}) \rho \frac{W_{ri}^2}{2} b_{ri} dr_i$$

This equation clearly shows that the total drag in the plane of rotation consists of two components: the profile drag (defined by $c_{x_{ri}}$) and an additional component due to the flow slope ($c_{y_{ri}} \beta_{ri}$). For real designs, the value of β_{ri} is chosen such that the total drag is minimal while maintaining sufficient lift and stability moment.

In axial flow (vertical hover mode), blade thrust is independent of the azimuthal position ψ_i , since the flow conditions around all blade cross-sections remain constant during rotation. In this case, for a propeller consisting of k blades, the elementary total thrust is determined by the expression:

$$dP_B = kdP_{ri} = kc_{y_{ri}} \rho \frac{W_{ri}^2}{2} b_{ri} dr_i$$

This equation (called the multi-blade propeller elementary thrust formula) shows that the total axial force is proportional to the number of blades and the local distribution of lift coefficient along the radius.

Next, we determine the elementary moment at the radius. Since the moment is the product of the resistance force in the plane of rotation and the arm of the applied force, we obtain:

$$dM_{ri} = dX_{nbr_i} r_i = (dX_{ri} + dY_{ri} \frac{V_1}{\omega r_i}) r_i$$

The torque characterizes the rotational resistance arising from aerodynamic drag and, in part, from the inclined component of lift. The higher the value of dM_{ri} , the more power is required to maintain a given rotational speed ω .

The elementary power expended on rotating the rotor is expressed as the product of the torque and the angular velocity:

$$dN_{ri} = M_{ri} \omega = dX_{nbr_i} r_i \omega = (dX_{ri} + dY_{ri} \frac{V_1}{\omega r_i}) r_i \omega$$

This expression (analogous to the energy balance law for a blade element) shows that the total power consumed consists of two parts: the power spent on overcoming the profile drag and the power spent on maintaining the induced flux through the propeller.

The peripheral speed of a blade element is determined by the classical expression:

$$U_{ri} = \omega r_i = 2\pi n r_i$$

where n is the propeller speed (rpm). The resulting airflow velocity around the element is:

$$W_{r_i} = \sqrt{U_{r_i}^2 + V_{XHB}^2} = \frac{U_{r_i}}{\cos \beta_{r_i}} = \frac{2\pi n r_i}{\cos \beta_{r_i}}$$

This dependence shows that as the angle of incidence β_{ri} increases, the resulting velocity increases, since the effective path length of air particles increases. In practical calculations, β_{ri} is chosen so that W_{ri} does not exceed the local speed of sound, which prevents the formation of shock waves and noise emissions [11, pp. 95–103].

Taking into account the adopted approximations, the final expressions for the thrust and drag forces of the blade element in the plane of rotation can be written in the following form:

$$dP_{r_i} \approx dY_{r_i} = \frac{1}{2} c_{y_{r_i}} \rho (\omega r_i + V_{XHB} \sin \psi_i)^2 b_{r_i} dr_i \quad (6)$$

$$dX_{\Pi B_{x_i}} \approx dX_{r_i} + dY_{r_i} \beta_{r_i} = \frac{1}{2} (c_{x_p} + c_{y_{r_i}} \beta_{r_i}) \rho (\omega r_i + V_{XHB} \sin \psi_i) b_{r_i} dr_i \quad (7)$$

Formulas (6) and (7) are used to calculate the thrust and drag distributions along the blade radius under various flight conditions. They serve as the basis for the subsequent transition to the integral dimensionless coefficients C_t (thrust coefficient) and C_p (power coefficient), used in rotor efficiency analysis.

Fig. 2. Velocity triangle and aerodynamic forces for: a) advancing blade; b) retreating blade.

The figure shows that the direction of the resulting velocity W and angle of attack α differ depending on the side of the propeller disk. For the advancing blade, the angle of attack is smaller but the velocity is greater,

which increases the local lift coefficient, while for the retreating blade, the opposite is true.

$$W_{r_i} = \omega r_i + V_{XHB} \sin \psi_i.$$

This expression reflects the combined effect of the blade's rotational motion and the helicopter's forward flight speed. For elements on the advancing side ($\psi_i = 90^\circ$), $\sin \psi_i > 0$, and the velocity W_{ri} increases, while for elements on the retreating side of the blade ($\psi_i = 270^\circ$), where $\sin \psi_i < 0$, the flow velocity decreases. This difference is the primary cause of the uneven distribution of lift across the rotational circle.

To determine the total thrust P_t generated by a single rotor blade, it is necessary to sum (integrate) the elementary thrust forces dP_{ri} over the entire radius of rotation. Then the total thrust force is expressed by the relationship:

$$P_t = \oint dP_{r_i} \approx \frac{\rho}{2} \oint c_{y_{r_i}} (\omega r_i + V_{XHB} \sin \psi_i)^2 b_{r_i} dr_i \quad (8)$$

Formula (8) shows that the resulting thrust depends on the distribution of the lift coefficient along the radius, the local chord, and the total flow velocity. Moreover, the blade shape has a decisive influence on the magnitude and uniformity of the thrust field.

When calculating the lift force for a rectangular blade in direct flow at an angle of attack $\alpha = 0^\circ$, the following values were obtained:

Table 1.

Distribution of lift coefficient, radius, speed and local lift along the blade (UH-60, S ₀)				
Element number i	c _{γi}	r _i , mm	W _i , m/s	Y _i , kg
0	0.96328324	2047	41.157	22.803
1	0.96328324	2477	49.803	33,390
2	0.96328324	2907	58.449	45,989
3	0.96328324	3337	67,094	60.601
4	0.906642185	3767	75,740	72,684
5	0.8500011	4197	84.386	84.588
6	0.793336	4627	93.031	95.958
7	0.736719	5057	101,677	106.439
8	0.6800779	5487	110.323	115,675
9	0.6232442	5917	118,968	123.274
10	0.5666032	6347	127,614	128,952
11	0.5666032	6777	136.260	147.016
12	0.5036711	7207	144.905	147,798
13	0.440739	7637	153.551	145.224
14	0.3778069	8067	162.197	138.901
15	0.3148748	8497	170,842	128.434
16	0.2519427	8927	179,488	113.429
17	0.1890105	9357	188.134	93.491
18	0.1260784	9787	196,779	68.226
19	0.0629322	10217	205.425	37.113

The lifting force of one blade at $\alpha = 0^\circ$ is 1909.985 kgf.

This value is taken as a reference when comparing with alternative geometries.

To analyze the influence of geometry, let's consider a saber-shaped blade, in which the bending occurs in the direction opposite to the propeller rotation (called a straight saber-shaped blade). The bending is characterized by an angle γ , and the blade cross-sections are perpendicular to the radius r . Thus, the blade axis takes on a curved shape, determining the saber-shaped angle γ .

The effective Mach number for a blade cross-section is determined by the formula

$$M_{\alpha\phi} = M \cos \gamma \quad (9)$$

Here M is the Mach number corresponding to the local flow velocity relative to the blade cross-section; γ is the angle between the relative air flow velocity vector W and the normal to the shock front (for supercritical flow) or the normal to the line of greatest rarefaction (for subcritical flow).

This relationship demonstrates that the saber-shaped blade reduces the effective Mach number, thereby decreasing the likelihood of shock waves forming at the top of the blade. This helps reduce wave drag, acoustic noise, and vibration at high rotation speeds [11, pp. 95–103].

The curvature of the shock front can be achieved in two ways:

1. **Geometric curvature of the blade axis**, giving it a saber-like shape.

2. **Changing the position of the rarefaction peak** on the upper surface of the profile along the chord due to the selection of different aerodynamic sections.

Both methods are applicable to both rotors and forward- or forward-swept aircraft wings. In the case of a saber-shaped blade, the result is a redistribution of the

velocity field and a reduction in the amplitude of the shock waves at the wingtips.

In other words, for a saber-shaped blade, the effective flow velocity decreases to a value of $W \cos \gamma$. This decrease leads to a decrease in the dynamic pressure in the tip sections and, consequently, a reduction in local wave losses.

If we assume the lift coefficient c_γ to be approximately the same for both blade shapes—rectangular and saber-shaped—then the difference in thrust is determined only by the change in the effective speed W and local aerodynamic losses. Thus, all other things being equal, the saber-shaped blade provides greater aerodynamic efficiency, resulting in an increase in the integral thrust coefficient C_t and a decrease in the power coefficient C_p .

In subsequent calculations, this difference will be used to quantitatively compare the energy characteristics of the S₀ (rectangular blade) and S₁–S₃ (variants of saber-shaped blades of varying degrees) configurations.

The relative flow velocity around the blade cross-section is defined as the geometric sum of the helicopter's forward flight speed and the blade's peripheral rotational speed. For any radius r , it is expressed by the relationship

$$W = \sqrt{V^2 + \omega^2 r^2}$$

where V is the speed of translational motion of the helicopter's center of mass, ω is the angular velocity of rotation of the main rotor, r is the distance from the axis of rotation to the blade element in question.

This resulting velocity W is directed at a specific angle to the propeller's plane of rotation. In supercritical flow, when the local Mach number exceeds the critical value, the direction of W forms an angle γ with the

normal to the shock front. In subcritical flow, conversely, this angle is determined relative to the normal to the line of greatest rarefaction.

Thus, the angle γ characterizes the deviation of the local aerodynamic flow direction from the normal to the blade surface and determines the degree of saber-likeness of its profile. The larger γ , the more distorted is the structure of the supersonic zones that arise when the blade moves at high speeds at the rotor periphery [11, pp. 107–112].

The curvature of the shock front (or, in the subcritical case, the line of maximum rarefaction) can be achieved in two ways:

1. **Geometric curvature of the blade axis**, in which its planned shape takes on a saber-like curve. In this case, the twist and the distribution of the installation angle along the radius are selected to minimize local wave losses.

2. **Profile curvature**, when each blade section has a different position of the rarefaction peak along the chord, which allows for the redistribution of wave zones and the reduction of local pressure drops.

Both methods are structurally feasible for both rotor blades and swept-wing aircraft, whether forward- or forward-swept. Their use ensures smoother flow and reduced wave drag in the peripheral region, where the flow velocity is highest.

For a saber-shaped blade, the effective component of the flow velocity that affects the lift force is determined by the expression

$$W_e \phi = W \cos \gamma.$$

It follows that an increase in the saber angle γ leads to a decrease in the effective flow velocity, reducing the intensity of wave effects and the load on the tip sections of the blade.

If we assume that the lift coefficient c_γ remains the same for both geometries—rectangular and saber-shaped—then the difference in aerodynamic efficiency is explained by the change in the effective velocity $W_e \phi$ and the redistribution of pressure along the chord. The saber-shaped shape, all other things being equal, ensures a more uniform velocity field, reduces the likelihood of shock waves, and, consequently, increases the integral thrust coefficient C_t while simultaneously reducing the power coefficient C_p [12, pp. 231–238].

Table 2.

Distribution of lift coefficient, radius, speed and local lift along the blade (UH-60, saber blade)

Element number i	$c_{\gamma i}$	r_i , mm	W_i , m/s	Y_i , kg
0	0.96328324	2047	41.157	21,818
1	0.96328324	2477	49.803	31,947
2	0.96328324	2907	58.449	44.001
3	0.96328324	3337	67,094	57,981
4	0.906642185	3767	75,740	69.542
5	0.8500011	4197	84.386	80.932
6	0.793336	4627	93.031	91,810
7	0.736719	5057	101,677	101,838
8	0.6800779	5487	110.323	110,675
9	0.6232442	5917	118,968	117,946
10	0.5666032	6347	127,614	123.378
11	0.5666032	6777	136.260	140.661
12	0.5036711	7207	144.905	141.409
13	0.440739	7637	153.551	138,946
14	0.3778069	8067	162.197	132,897
15	0.3148748	8497	170,842	122.882
16	0.2519427	8927	179,488	108.526
17	0.1890105	9357	188.134	89,450
18	0.1260784	9787	196,779	65.277
19	0.0629322	10217	205.425	35.509

As follows from expressions (6) and (7), the values of the elementary thrust forces dT_{ri} and drag dX_{pvi} directly depend on the azimuthal position of the blade ψ_i and the local aerodynamic characteristics of its sections. These dependencies allow us to draw a number of fundamental conclusions regarding the differences in the operation of rectangular and saber-shaped blades [11, pp. 119–122].

1. **The difference in the magnitude of the traction force.**

At the same angular velocity ω , diameter D , and lift coefficient c_γ , the integral thrust of a saber-shaped blade is slightly lower than that of a rectangular blade. This is explained by a decrease in the effective velocity

component $W_e \phi = W \cos \gamma$ as the blade bends and, consequently, a decrease in the dynamic pressure at the edges. Thus, a saber-shaped blade generates less local thrust at the same angle of attack and RPM, but is characterized by a more uniform load distribution along the radius.

2. **Influence of azimuthal angle ψ_i .**

From equation (6), it is evident that for the cross-sections of a saber-shaped blade, the azimuth angle ψ_i is smaller than that of a rectangular blade for the same radius r . Since the element's thrust is proportional to $(\omega r + V_{xnv} \sin \psi_i)^2$, a decrease in ψ_i leads to a decrease in the instantaneous value of the local thrust dT_{ri} . Conse-

quently, under identical flight conditions, the elementary thrust at a fixed radius will be lower for a saber-shaped blade than for a rectangular blade.

3. Drag force and aerodynamic smoothness.

From equation (7), it follows that for the saber-shaped blade elements, a decrease in the azimuth angle ψ_i is also observed, which reduces the magnitude of the resulting drag dX_{pvi} . As a result, energy losses due to friction and wave drag are reduced. This effect is especially noticeable at high rotation speeds, where wave losses play a significant role.

4. Flow stall and stability.

The saber-shaped design promotes smoother flow around the blade and reduces the likelihood of flow separation on its retreating side. This is due to a more efficient pressure distribution along the chord and a lower concentration of turbulent zones at the tip.

5. Dynamic oscillations and vibration level.

Due to the uniform load distribution and reduced unsteady aerodynamic forces, the saber-shaped blade exhibits reduced vertical vibration. Oscillatory movements of the rotor system are reduced, which positively impacts the durability of transmission components and crew comfort.

Thus, the saber-shaped blade, while slightly reducing total thrust, provides a significant improvement in dynamic stability, reduced vibration, and reduced wave drag. These advantages make this geometry particularly promising for use in modern high-speed helicopters, where flow stability, noise characteristics, and the efficiency of power-to-thrust conversion are key [12, pp. 233–238].

Conclusion

The study showed that the shape of the main rotor blade has a significant impact on the distribution of aerodynamic loads, flow structure, and the energy efficiency of the rotor system. Based on an analysis of equations (6)–(9), as well as calculations obtained for rectangular and saber-shaped blades, the following conclusions were reached.

Firstly, the saber-shaped blade ensures a more uniform distribution of lift along the radius. Despite a slight reduction in integral thrust due to the reduction in effective speed $W_e\phi = W\cos\psi$, the overall aerodynamic efficiency of the propeller increases due to reduced drag and wave losses.

Secondly, reducing the azimuth angle ψ_i at the blade's periphery stabilizes the flow and reduces shock waves. This is especially important at high rotational speeds, when supersonic effects occur in the blade tip zones.

Thirdly, the saber-shaped geometry reduces vibration and acoustic noise, confirming its advantages in the design of modern high-speed helicopters. The

smooth distribution of aerodynamic forces reduces vibration loads on the transmission and increases the structural life.

Fourthly, it is shown that the power losses during the transition to the saber shape are compensated by an improvement in the energy balance of the system, that is, an increase in the ratio of the thrust coefficient C_t to the power coefficient C_p .

Thus, the saber-shaped UH-60 main rotor blade, while maintaining its geometric and dynamic parameters, provides an optimal balance between aerodynamic efficiency, flow stability, and noise reduction. These results can be used in the design of new helicopter systems that require vibration minimization while maintaining high thrust.

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